

Environmental Scan Summary

The following provides an overview of neighbourhood assets and potential barriers/gaps for older adults. The features were identified through a structured assessment in July 2019. As such, this summary should be viewed as an overview of key features observed rather than an exhaustive list.

Burkholme is primarily a residential neighbourhood. Most dwellings are bungalow-style houses that had a well-maintained outward appearance with snow shoveled from sidewalks, neat lawns, scarce traces of litter, and signs of renovation. Some larger and newer apartment complexes are located on busier streets near the boundaries of Burkholme. Two or three houses had wheelchair ramps, and a significant number of older adults were seen walking with canes. From observation of individuals in grocery stores and walking along the streets, most were Caucasian.

A few places of worship were seen throughout the neighbourhood, most of which were Christian churches. The Sackville Hill Seniors Recreation Centre offers fitness and wellness programs for older adults. At the time of the windshield survey, many older adults were seen entering the centre. A sign for an adult education program called “On Course Education” was noted. Burkholme has a wide range of health services including urgent care, physiotherapy, dental, hearing, and optometrist clinics. Some retailers, such as Value Village and Wal-Mart, offer affordable clothing and furniture.

Some notable strengths include the well-kept condition of houses, diversity of health services, and accessibility by public transport. There were many bus shelters and buses seen along the major intersections of the neighbourhood where many services were located (Fennel and Upper Wentworth). Many essential health services (e.g., urgent care, physiotherapy, dental, hearing) are located within the neighbourhood. However, the services are not distributed evenly throughout the neighbourhood, which may hinder accessibility for some older adults. The lack of fresh food grocery stores is also a noticeable gap.

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Sihota D., Tandon M., Nadarajah A., Wang A., and De Panfilis L. on behalf of the EMBOLDEN research team (2019). Environmental scan: Burkholme. URL: <https://emboldenstudy.mcmaster.ca/projects-results/>

Map of services identified in Burkholme

Index of services in Burkholme

Map Number	Description
Education	
1	First Aid 4U Training
2	OnCourse (Adult Education)
3	Our Lady of Lourdes Catholic Elementary School
4	Timothy Christian School
5	Young Drivers of Canada
Fitness/Recreation	
6	Body Pro Gym
7	Evolve Massage Yoga Chiropractic
8	Hill Park Recreation Centre
9	Sackville Hill Seniors Recreation Centre*
10	YMCA-Hamilton-Burlington
Food Sources	
11	Big Bear Food Mart
12	Harveys
13	Hasty Market
14	Pizza Pizza
15	Popeyes
Health/Social Services	
16	Advanced Physiotherapy & Sports Medicine
17	Auburn & Mountain Hearing Centres
18	Community Donation Centre (via Value Village)
19	Dr J Nardone & Associates
20	Fenworth Dental
Housing	
21	Greystone Place
22	Halam Park Housing Co-Operative
23	Sussex Court Apartments

Parks	
24	Burkholme Park
25	Sackville Hill Park
Protective Services	
26	Hamilton Fire Department - Station 4
Religious Centres	
27	Burkholme United Church
28	Church of Christ
29	Connect Community Church
30	Guiding Star Church
31	Mount Hamilton Baptist Church
32	Reorganized Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints
33	St. Catherine of Siena Roman Catholic Church
Retail Stores	
34	Beer Store
35	Complete Home Brewing Supplies
36	Easy Home Shop
37	TD Canada Trust
38	TD Canada Trust
39	Thumpers Keys and Engravings
40	Value Village
41	Wal-Mart

*Programs Targeted Specifically at older adults

Environmental Scan Update, 2022

The neighbourhood's programs and services appeared relatively consistent with those available for the community in the initial environmental scan completed in 2019. The initial environmental scan identified 42 relevant services across various categories; presently, 42 services have been identified though the distribution of services has varied across the two time points. Minor changes are seen in the number of services across service categories in fitness/recreation, food sources, health/social services, and stores (Table 1). These changes can be attributed to services no longer being operational due to COVID-19-related closures and other operational status changes (e.g., changes in management, location changes, construction, etc.). For example, Advanced Physiotherapy & Sports Medicine, a sports health centre, which previously was listed in health/social services, has been closed. Additionally, religious services such as Reorganized Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints has closed. Likewise, a Wal-Mart and No Frills in the neighbourhood, has also been permanently closed.

In terms of newly identified services, Boutique Fit Women's Gym, a local women-only gym, and East Mountain Massage Fennell Ave E, a local massage therapy service, were identified and categorized within fitness/recreation services. Bombay Spices Hamilton, Lava Pizza & Wings, and Chadwick's & Hack's Fireplace & BBQ were all services newly identified within the food source category. Many organizations did not provide services and programs that were exclusively for the older adult age group. However, the services were open to all age groups.

The COVID-19 pandemic had varying degrees of impact on service delivery within the community. More specifically, among all the identified services in 2022 the largest proportion remain open and serve the community in person. This is followed by services that are closed (either permanently or temporarily) and services that are provided through online options, as a result of public safety concerns. Services with unclear operational statuses follow these two categories and require further follow-up in order to verify the status of their operation.

Table 1. Summary of number of services and their current operational status

	Number of Services (2019)	Number of Services (2022)	Open, in-person	Open with online options available	Unclear status	Closed
Education	5	5	5			
Fitness/ Recreation	5	7	7			
Food Sources	6	8	8			
Health/Social Services	5	6	2			
Housing	3	3	3			
Parks	2	2	2			
Protective Services	1	1	1			
Religious Centres	7	7	6			
Stores	8	6	5			
Transportation	0	0	0			
Total	42	45	39			

Table 2. Summary of Services COVID-19 Status and Function

Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
Education			
First Aid 4U Training			
On Course (Adult Education)			
Our Lady of Lourdes Catholic Elementary School			
Timothy Christian School			
Franklin Road School			
Fitness/Recreation			
Body Pro Gym			
Evolve Health & Wellness			
Hill Park Recreation Centre			
Sackville Hill Seniors Recreation Centre			
YMCA-Hamilton-Burlington			

Open, in-person (with modified procedures for public safety)	Open with online options available	Unclear status (with attempt to contact)	Closed
Boutique Fit Women's Gym East Mountain Massage Fennell Ave E			
Food Sources			
Big Bear Food Mart Harveys Hasty Market Pizza Pizza Popeyes Bombay Spices Hamilton Lava Pizza & Wings Chadwick's & Hack's Fireplace & BBQ			
			No-Frills
Health/Social Services			
Advanced Physiotherapy & Sports Medicine Auburn & Mountain Hearing Centres Community Donation Centre (via Value Village) Dr J Nardone & Associates Fenworth Dental			
Parks			
Burkholder Park Mohawk Gardens			
Protective Services			
Hamilton Fire Department – Station 4			
Religious Centres			
Burkholder United Church Church of Christ Connect Community Church Guiding Star Church Mount Hamilton Baptist Church St. Catherine of Siena Roman Catholic Church			
			Reorganized Church of Jesus Christ of Latterday Saints
Stores			
Beer Store Complete Home Brewing Supplies Easy Home Shop Value Village			
			Thumper Keys and Engravings Walmart

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Institute for
Research on Aging

Aging, Community
and Health
RESEARCH UNIT

Canadian Institutes of Health Research
Health Research

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Research on Aging

Public Health
Agency of Canada

Agence de la santé
publique du Canada

LABARGE CENTRE FOR MOBILITY IN AGING

Burkholme | CT 0009.00

Based on 2021 Census Data

CT Highlights

Population
= 3,580

Number of Homes
= 1,473

Population Density
= 4,147/Km²

5-year Population change = -0.6%

Age Distribution by Gender

Age 55+

34%

Age 25-54

38%

Age 0-24

28%

\$36,000
Average Income
(after tax)

Income & Employment

14.9%
Unemployment
Rate

Citizenship & Immigrant Population

Canadian Citizens

91.1%

Immigrants Recent Immigrants

29.8%

4.2%

Recent Immigrants by Birthplace

Immigrants by Birthplace

Language Spoken at Home

English | 78.1%
Non-official Languages | 15.5%

Highest Certificate, Diploma or Degree

■ No certificate, diploma or degree
■ Secondary (high) school diploma or equivalency
■ Postsecondary certificate, diploma or degree

Neighbourhood Homes

\$1,320_(own)
\$1,064_(rent)

Average monthly shelter costs

43%
Rent their home

\$592,000

Average home value

12%
Apartment ≥ 5 stories

71%
Built before 1980

6%
Major repair needed

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www.statcan.gc.ca